

CYBERSTAND.eu

Engaging & supporting EU experts in Cybersecurity Standardisation activities

Standards and SMEs: How standards can benefit smaller enterprises

**CYBERSTAND
ONLINE WEBINAR**
3rd April 2025

Post-Event report

Co-funded by
the European Union

ECCC
EUROPEAN CYBERSECURITY
COMPETENCE CENTRE

Funded by
the European Union

SMEs often struggle to engage with standards due to their complexity and cost to implement. However, adopting standards can lead to stronger business relationships, greater market access and new technical innovations.

Through discussions with standards experts from small business representatives, this webinar will explore how standards can be beneficial tools for SMEs, rather than costly barriers. Understanding the standardisation process and how SMEs are able to contribute to this can lead to new opportunities, greater expertise and more trustworthy products.

Currently, the majority of standards are not drafted with SMEs in mind. The only resolution to this is to include more SME voices in the standardisation process, and the Cyberstand.eu project can provide support to do so.

Learn more about how SMEs can benefit from standards and become involved in the standards creation process through this webinar, hosted by DIGITAL SME, Small Business Standards and Cyberstand.

Event Takeaways:

Many SMEs lack the time and resources to engage directly in standardization work, which can demand significant weekly commitment. To address this, organizations like SBS and the Digital SME Alliance support SMEs by representing their interests, collecting and sharing their input, and helping them participate indirectly through shared efforts.

By actively engaging in standardization processes SMEs can help shape rules that impact their business directly. This involvement not only gives them a voice in industry direction but also builds awareness of upcoming challenges, and positions them as credible, forward-thinking players in their field.

Standards should be developed by companies that bring their market experience to the table, and the standardization process must be inclusive, open, and transparent, allowing even smaller companies to actively contribute, have an impact, and propose standards.

Efforts are underway to increase awareness and participation in the standardization process among professionals. This includes creating opportunities for gradual involvement, recognizing that contributing effectively requires time, education, and alignment across bodies such as ETSI, CEN-CENELEC, especially in response to the growing complexity and pressure of new cybersecurity regulations.

Insights from the experts:

“Essentially, anything that’s connected to the internet now will have a minimal set of cybersecurity requirements. There is a standardization process underway to create the standards to support this, and Cyberstand is helping experts join this process.”

James Philpot (European Digital SME Alliance)

“SMEs, as much as we try, are still underrepresented in standardization. That is why we need a stronger role: on the one hand, to be granted and to be able to have it from decision-makers, policy makers, and from European standardization organizations, and on the other hand, on our side what we can do to indeed boost participation.”

Andrea Raffaelli (Small Business Standards)

“Standards are often perceived as complex and resource intensive, particularly when it comes to SMEs. However, they are also very powerful tools that can drive growth, innovation and competitiveness

Anthony Senter (SDWAN Solutions)

“We have to ask ourselves: when a standardization action is needed? Because it’s an endeavor, right? I have to put effort into that, so I have to evaluate the cost and opportunities. So when a standardization action is needed? And the answer is, for me, whenever interoperability is critical for you to offer a service to your customers”

Dario Sabella (Next G Cloud Technologies)

CYBERSTAND.eu

Engaging & supporting EU experts in Cybersecurity Standardisation activities

Watch the recording!

cyberstand.eu

 [@CYBERSTANDEU](https://twitter.com/CYBERSTANDEU)

 [/company/cyberstandeu/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/cyberstandeu/)

 zenodo.org/records/14046547

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union

ECCC
EUROPEAN CYBERSECURITY
COMPETENCE CENTRE